

SECTOR WISE GROSS DISTRICT DOMESTIC PRODUCT AT CURRENT AND CONSTANT PRICE IN VIDARBHA REGION

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Abstract

The study was conducted under the eleven district of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra, namely Akola, Amravati, Bhandara, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Gondia, Nagpur, Wardha, Washim, Yavatmal with the objective to study the growth rate of sector wise Gross District Domestic Product at current and constant price. The data of sector wise GDDP were based on secondary data which was collected from the period 2002-03 to 2021-22. The analysis reveal a balanced yet varied development across Vidarbha districts, with notable strengths in different sectors depending on the district, reflecting the region's economic diversification and transformation over the years. Some areas like Gondia, Gadchiroli, Amravati showed strong performances across multiple sectors, particularly in Washim, which demonstrates significant growth across the board. The data suggests that Vidarbha's economy is becoming increasingly diversified, with different districts specializing in different sectors, leading to a more balanced regional development. In the over all region of Vidarbha there was increase in the growth of secondary sector both at current and constant price while the other sector reveal a modest growth rate in the region.

Keywords: Compound growth rate, coefficient of variation, Gross district domestic product, Vidarbha.

Introduction

Gross Domestic Product is one of the key indicators to measure the economic growth and status of the country. Therefore, to reveal variations in the economic growth at ground/sub state level District Domestic Product is considered as one of the most important indicators to measure the economic growth of a district and also estimates of per capita income of districts measures the standard of living of inhabitants of the districts. Analyzing the Gross District Domestic Product provides valuable perception into the region's economic dynamics across the various sectors. The growth rate of Gross District Domestic Product is a key measure to analyse the economic progression of the region over a period of time. It highlights the rate at which whether the economy is expanding or contracting, revealing the perspective on the overall economic growth and development progress of Vidarbha. A positive growth rate indicates economic expansion, while a negative growth rate suggests a contraction. The Coefficient of Variation (CV) of GDDP, on the other hand, is a statistical measure that determines the extent of variability in the GDDP relative to its mean. It is particularly useful in understanding the stability and consistency of economic growth across the districts of Vidarbha. A higher CV indicates greater fluctuations in economic performance, suggesting uneven growth across different sectors over a time period and vice versa, a lower CV suggests more steady growth, indicating a stable economic progress. By analyzing the growth rate and CV of GDDP in Vidarbha, this study aims to provide a detailed understanding of the region's economic performance, highlighting growth, disparities, and potential areas of concern or opportunity for future economic planning and development.

Material and methods

Selection of study area:

The present study on the dynamics of Gross District Domestic Product (GDDP) in Vidarbha i.e, Akola, Amravati, Bhandara, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Gondia, Nagpur, Wardha, Washim, Yavatmal were conducted using secondary data sources. The study area provides a distinctive opportunity to examine into the complex economic characteristic of Vidarbha region and also provides a closer look at its economic growth and development.

Study period:

The data on Gross District Domestic Product from the past 20 years were obtained from published sources. For analysis of constant and current prices, the data was collected from the period 2002-03 to 2021-22.

Analytical tools and techniques:

Estimation of growth rate

The growth rates were used to measure the past performance of the economic variables. The growth of sector-wise and district-wise GDDP growth rates was analyzed for period (2002-03 to 2012-2022) using the exponential growth function with the given formula:

$$Y=ab^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where,

- Y= Sector wise GDDP
- t= Time variable
- b=Regression coefficient
- a=Intercept

The equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } y= \text{Log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

The compound growth rates 'r' were computed by using the following formula.

$$\text{CGR}(r)= [\text{Antilog } (\log b)-1] \times 100$$

Where,

r= compound growth rate

Coefficient of variation (CV):

The coefficient of variation for current and constant prices at all sectors under district wise was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Coefficient of variation (CV)} = \text{S.D}/\text{Mean} \times 100$$

S = Standard deviation

\bar{X} = Arithmetic means.

X = Variable

n = Number of observation

Result and discussion

The estimation of the growth rate was to understand and determine the economic growth in the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra and to know its progress in each district in a distinctive manner to measure the stability of economic development.

Table 1: Compound growth rate of Gross district domestic product at current price of Vidarbha.

District	Primary Sector	Secondary Sector	Tertiary Sector
Akola	10.93**	14.91**	13.98**
Amravati	11.38**	16.76**	15.14**
Bhandara	11.21**	10.43**	11.51**
Buldhana	12.27**	14.86**	14.34**
Chandrapur	9.01**	10.96**	9.81**

Gadchiroli	9.66**	16.31**	16.49**
Gondia	13.15**	12.66**	14.77**
Nagpur	8.49**	12.82**	12.20**
Wardha	11.43**	13.96**	13.51**
Washim	12.18**	18.11**	16.82**
Yavatmal	10.07**	15.24**	12.43**
Vidarbha	10.65**	13.52**	12.74**

NOTE: **= significance at 1 per cent

The above Table No.1 shows that compound growth rates (CGR) of the primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors across the districts of Vidarbha from 2002-03 to 2021-22 show distinct patterns of economic development. In primary sector, districts like Gondia, Washim, and Buldhana exhibit the highest growth rates at 13.15 per cent per annum, 12.18 per cent per annum, and 12.27 per cent per annum, respectively, indicating a strong agricultural performance. While Nagpur and Chandrapur show relatively lower growth rates at 8.49 per cent per annum and 9.01 per cent per annum, resulting a lesser dependency on agriculture.

The secondary sector witnessed significant growth across most districts, with Washim leading at 18.11 per cent per annum, followed closely by Gadchiroli (16.31 per cent per annum) and Amravati (16.76 per cent per annum) which signifies industrialization in these areas. Bhandara and Chandrapur, however, recorded lower growth rates of 10.43 per cent per annum and 10.96 per cent per annum, indicating more moderate industrial expansion.

In the tertiary sector, which includes services, Gadchiroli and Washim again stand out with the highest growth rates of 16.49 per cent per annum and 16.82 per cent per annum, respectively, highlighting a surge in service-based activities. Meanwhile, Yavatmal, Nagpur, and Chandrapur have lower growth rates of 12.43 per cent per annum, 12.20 per cent per annum, and 9.81 per cent per annum, respectively, though still indicating healthy expansion in the services sector.

Vidarbha's overall average growth rates are moderate compared to individual districts. The region has a balanced performance with the primary sector at 10.65 per cent per annum, the secondary sector at 13.52 per cent per annum, and the tertiary sector at 12.74 per cent per annum. The table highlights the variability in economic growth across different districts and sectors in Vidarbha.

The study by Namrata Anand (2014) showed the growth dynamics altering the structure of Indian economy with a decline in the share of agriculture and gain in the service sectors which was similar to the findings of the decline of growth rate of agriculture and the rise in the other sector of the Vidarbha region.

Table 2: Compound growth rate of Gross district domestic product at constant price of Vidarbha.

District	Primary Sector	Secondary Sector	Tertiary Sector
Akola	9.91**	14.12**	13.33**
Amravati	10.70**	16.10**	14.46**
Bhandara	8.88**	9.71**	10.22**
Buldhana	10.21**	14.29**	13.24**
Chandrapur	7.56**	10.41**	9.00**
Gadchiroli	8.29**	15.57**	15.40**
Gondia	11.19**	12.05**	13.75**
Nagpur	6.87**	12.29**	11.44**
Wardha	9.48**	13.27**	12.54**
Washim	12.59**	17.58**	15.94**
Yavatmal	8.89**	14.55**	11.47**
Vidarbha	9.48**	13.22**	12.32**

NOTE: **= significance at 1 per cent

The compound growth rates (CGR) for the primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors across Vidarbha's districts from 2002-03 to 2021-22 highlight several economic growth patterns.

In the primary sector, Washim leads with a CGR of 12.59 per cent showing a strong agricultural foundation. Gondia and Buldhana also show notable growth at 11.19 per cent per annum and 10.21 per cent per annum, respectively. On the other hand, districts like Nagpur and Chandrapur exhibit lower growth rates of 6.87 per cent per annum and 7.56 per cent per annum, indicating a gradual shift away from agriculture.

The secondary sector has experienced significant growth in most districts, particularly in Washim, which shows the highest CGR at 17.58 per cent per annum, followed by Gadchiroli at 15.57 per cent per annum and Amravati at 16.10 per annum per cent signifying industrial activity in these regions. However, Bhandara and Chandrapur report more modest growth rates of 9.71 per cent and 10.41 per cent per annum, respectively.

The tertiary sector growth is also pronounced, with Washim, Gadchiroli, and Gondia leading at 15.94 per cent per annum, 15.40 per

cent per annum, and 13.75 per cent per annum, respectively, indicating a strong expansion in services and Nagpur and Chandrapur have comparatively lower growth rates of 11.44 per cent per annum and 9.00 per cent per annum, but still reflect substantial growth in the services sector.

Overall, these growth rates reveal the varied economic dynamics across Vidarbha's districts, with some areas showing strong performances across different sectors, particularly in Washim, which demonstrates significant growth across the board. The data suggests that Vidarbha's economy is becoming increasingly diversified, with different districts specializing in different sectors, leading to a more balanced regional development.

Priyanka Tariyal (2016) reported that secondary sector turned out to be the lead sectors in pulling the overall growth of the economy whereas agriculture continues to be the important sector despite having the lowest contribution to output which shows a similar study with the growth rate of Vidarbha at both current and constant price.

Table 3: Coefficient of variation of sector wise Gross District Domestic Product at current price in Vidarbha region.

District	Primary Sector	Secondary Sector	Tertiary Sector
Akola	63.21	68.31	64.74
Amravati	58.90	74.71	68.91
Bhandara	59.84	49.73	54.47
Buldhana	85.82	64.51	65.86
Chandrapur	51.03	48.87	47.06
Gadchiroli	47.97	73.93	74.84
Gondia	72.39	58.90	69.56
Nagpur	49.53	55.86	55.35
Wardha	66.25	61.88	61.33
Washim	64.48	73.65	72.19
Yavatmal	53.74	67.41	58.23
Vidarbha	57.44	60.03	58.78

The above Table No.3 shows coefficient of variation rates of the primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors across the districts of Vidarbha at current price from the period 2002-03 to 2021-22.

In the primary sector, Buldhana stands out with the highest growth rate at 85.82 per cent, indicating a strong agricultural activity in this sector. Gondia and Washim also show notable growth at 72.39 per cent and 64.48 per cent, respectively, highlighting the importance of agriculture in these districts. Following by Gadchiroli and Nagpur report lower growth rates of 47.97 per cent and 49.53 per cent, respectively, suggesting a more subdued performance in agricultural activities.

The secondary sector has seen substantial growth in several districts, particularly Amravati, which leads with a 74.71 per cent growth rate, reflecting significant industrial development. Gadchiroli and Washim also exhibit high growth rates at 73.93 per cent and 73.65 per cent, respectively, indicating expansion in manufacturing and related industries. In contrast, Chandrapur and Bhandara have lower growth

rates of 48.87 per cent and 49.73 per cent, respectively, indicating slower industrial growth.

The tertiary sector also demonstrates strong growth across most districts, with Gadchiroli leading at 74.84 per cent, followed by Amravati and Washim at 68.91 per cent and 72.19 per cent, respectively, underscoring the increasing importance of services in these regions. On the other hand, Chandrapur and Nagpur exhibit lower growth rates of 47.06 per cent and 55.35 per cent, respectively, though they still show substantial service sector expansion.

Overall, the data sets a diverse economic landscape in Vidarbha, with some districts like Gadchiroli, Washim, and Amravati showing strong growth across multiple sectors, particularly in services and industry. Meanwhile, districts like Buldhana and Gondia highlight the continued significance of the primary sector. This variation in growth rates across sectors and districts reflects the differing economic strengths and dynamics development within the Vidarbha region.

Table 4: Coefficient of variation of sector wise Gross District Domestic Product at constant price in Vidarbha region.

District	Primary Sector	Secondary Sector	Tertiary Sector
Akola	57.30	70.58	64.33
Amravati	65.21	77.04	69.30
Bhandara	62.26	50.65	50.94
Buldhana	74.91	67.71	61.70
Chandrapur	46.44	50.39	45.58
Gadchiroli	51.27	75.98	73.41
Gondia	72.51	61.55	67.27
Nagpur	47.94	58.07	54.43
Wardha	60.83	63.49	59.15
Washim	74.96	76.97	71.69
Yavatmal	53.90	69.38	56.37
Vidarbha	57.99	63.79	59.05

The Table no.4 shows the coefficient of variation in the primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors across Vidarbha's districts which highlight diverse economic developments and sectoral performances.

In the primary sector, districts like Washim and Buldhana lead with impressive growth rates of 74.96 per cent and 74.91 per cent, respectively, showing strong agricultural activities. Gondia also shows significant growth at 72.51 per cent, emphasizing its agricultural resilience. On the lower end, Chandrapur and Nagpur report growth rates of 46.44 per cent and 47.94 per cent, respectively, indicating a more modest performance in agriculture.

The secondary sector shows substantial industrial growth in districts like Amravati and Washim, with growth rates of 77.04 per cent and 76.97 per cent, respectively, showing industrial development. Gadchiroli also demonstrates strong industrial expansion with a growth rate of 75.98 per cent. In contrast, Chandrapur and Bhandara display lower growth rates of 50.39 per cent and 50.65 per cent, suggesting slower industrial progress.

In the tertiary sector, Gadchiroli leads with a growth rate of 73.41 per cent, highlighting a strong expansion in services. Washim and Amravati follow closely with growth rates of 71.69 per cent and 69.30 per cent, respectively, indicating a growing service sector in these districts. On the other hand, Chandrapur and Bhandara exhibit lower growth rates of 45.58 per cent and 50.94 per cent, respectively, though they still reflect significant service sector development.

Overall, the data reveals in Vidarbha, with districts like Washim, Amravati, and Gadchiroli showed strong performances across multiple sectors, particularly in industry and services. Meanwhile, districts such as Buldhana and Gondia continue to excel in the primary sector, while others like Chandrapur and Nagpur show more balanced yet moderate growth across all sectors. This diversity in growth rates underscores the different economic development and sectoral strengths within the Vidarbha region.

Bhopale, A.A., & Shende, N.V. (2021) reported consistent findings showing high variability in production and area aligning with the high

coefficient of variation in soybean noting a similarity in the coefficient of variation of sector wise in Vidarbha region.

Conclusions and Implications

The study of Gross District Domestic Product (GDDP) in Vidarbha, Maharashtra from 2002-03 to 2021-22 shows a diverse economic picture with different growth patterns across sectors and districts. Districts like Gondia, Washim, and Buldhana have seen strong growth in agriculture, while Nagpur and Chandrapur have shown less growth, indicating a move away from farming. The secondary sector, which includes industries, has grown significantly, especially in Washim, Gadchiroli, and Amravati, showing an increase in industrial activities. The tertiary sector, covering services, also shows strong growth in Gadchiroli, Washim, and Gondia. Over all the district, Washim shows highest growth, another addition to this reason is that it is a new district which is why the share of GDDP share were more as compared to the rest of the district. Overall, Vidarbha's economy is becoming more balanced and diversified, with the secondary sector leading in growth. The findings suggest several important actions. Authority should focus on strengthening the key sectors in each district. For example, supporting agriculture in districts like Washim and Buldhana, and boosting industrial and service sectors in places like Washim and Gadchiroli, could improve economic outcomes. The diverse growth patterns determine the need for continued support for various sectors to ensure balanced regional development. Investment opportunities are particularly good in districts with strong growth in agriculture, industry, or services. Addressing regional differences through targeted strategies can help improve overall economic performance and balance. Future research should explore what drives these growth differences and how specific policies impact them, providing better outlook for effective planning. This study offers a clear view of Vidarbha's economic strengths and challenges, guiding future development efforts.

References

1. **Anand M (2014)** An overview of Indian economy: 1991-2013. *J Econ and Finance* 3: 19-24.
2. **Bhopale, A.A., & Shende, N.V. 2021.** Performance of Cost n prices of soybean in Vidarbha. *Economic affairs*, 66(4), 549-554.
3. **Ghosh M (2006)** Regional convergence in Indian agriculture. *Ind J Agric Econ* 61: 610-629
4. **Gorji, A. and Alipour, M., 2006,** Study the effect of liberalization on economic growth of OPEC countries. *Quarterly Journal of Commercial Studies*, 40(2):187-203
5. **Kaur M and Kaur M (2000)** Structural adjustments in Punjab economy with special reference to agriculture sector. *J Agric Dev Policy* **12: 25-32.**
6. **Majumdar, R. 2005.** Growth and development an Indian experience, Department of Economic, University lib. of Munich Germany.MPRA paper 4850. <http://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/4850/1/MPRA-paper-4850>.
7. **Mishra D K (2006)** Institutional specificities and agrarian transformation in Arunachal Pradesh: Changing realities and emerging challenges. *Ind J Agri Econ* 61: 314-327.
8. **Sawant S D and Achutan C V (1995)** Agricultural growth across crops and regions: Emerging patterns and trends. *Econ and Pol Wkly* 30: A2-A13
9. **Singh P and Singh A (1999)** Dynamics of intra-sectoral imbalances in agriculture: A case study of Punjab and Bihar. *The Bihar J Agril Mktg* 6: 2-11.
10. **Tariyal P (2016)** Structural change in Indian Economy: changing composition of growth. *Int J Social Sciences and Humanities Res* 4: 492-500.
11. **Walunj, Renuka. (2014).** The study of GDP Growth Rates of India: An Empirical Study, conference paper on Innovative management & technological tools as economic growth engines in Indian perspective.2014: 152-155.